

Dissemination and Communication Plan Water-ForCE

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List of Acronyms

CRM	Customer Relationship Management Software
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DOCP	Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environmental Agency
ESA	European Space Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JRC	Joint Research Center
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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1 Purpose and Scope

This document contains the Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Plan (DOCP) for the Water-ForCE Coordination and Support Action (CSA). This DOCP will be a reference framework for evaluating the impact of dissemination and communication activities and will be updated and adjusted as the project progresses.

The Water-ForCE project DOCP has been structured in various sections presenting the communication and dissemination objectives, target audiences, messages and implementation measures. This deliverable aims to guarantee the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication regarding the project's goals, activities and outcomes.

2 Water-ForCE Overview

Data products related to the water and hydrological parameters are being developed and examples can be found across all six Copernicus Services. However, the development of these data products tends to be undertaken in isolation of each other and in response to specific challenges without consideration of the global perspective, understanding or better representation of the water cycle from regional to global scales. In order to avoid duplication between the six Services, to improve the understanding of the water cycle and to provide better services to the wider user community, the European Commission had a call for the Coordination and Support Action projects: "Copernicus evolution: Mission exploitation concept for WATER". The expectation from the call is that the successful project consortium will provide the best long-term mission concept for water.

The overarching objective of the Water-ForCE project is to develop a Roadmap for Copernicus inland water services. **The Roadmap will provide a user and stakeholder driven concept for water services** (water quantity, water quality, hydrological parameters, ice, snow, etc.) by assessing the existing and emerging needs, the opportunities presented by the current and future technical capabilities of satellite and in situ sensors, and addressing the current disconnects between remote sensing, in situ observations and modelling communities. Critically, the Roadmap will deliver the clarity required in relation to the needs and expectations of the core Copernicus mission by the public and private sectors and the wider research and business innovation opportunities.

Water-ForCE aims to bring together experts on water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors. This will include the relevant Copernicus Services (Atmosphere, Marine, Land, Climate Change, Security, Energy) and Networks (Copernicus Academy and Copernicus Relays), ESA, H2020 projects and international organizations as well as public and private research organizations. By working with these communities, Water-ForCE will deliver:

- A Roadmap for the water component of future Copernicus services defining which is the most optimal long-term strategy that takes into account that existing water related products are split and distributed across the six Copernicus Services.
- The technical requirements for future Copernicus missions to fulfil better inland and coastal water related needs (e.g. optimal configuration of Sentinel-2E and onward, CHIME hyperspectral sensor etc).
- An enlarged service portfolio, containing higher level biogeochemical products, improved performance of the current products and products that integrate across water quality and water quantity.

- The closer cooperation between remote sensing, *in situ* and modelling communities in order to build an optimal network that provides necessary information about inland and coastal waters to policy makers, managers, researchers and the general public.

2.1 Concept

The Copernicus Inland Water Services Roadmap will include all different aspects of the WATER services starting from the EU directives where the Services can or should be used and ending with proposed technical requirements for the next generation of Copernicus sensors and a framework that will structure future research and innovation that will minimise duplication and maximise the opportunity in the production of WATER products provided by Copernicus Services and the resulting value chain.

In order to achieve this, we developed a **work concept that consists of four overarching WPs and four technical WPs**. The first overarching **WP1** will analyse current and future policies, end-users needs, innovation needs, need for supporting water related SDG's, etc.

Figure 1: Water-ForCE project overall concept

The technical WPs are: Water quality continuum (WP2), Water quantity (WP3), Aligning *in situ* and satellite Earth observation activities (WP4) and modelling and data assimilation (WP5). Each of the technical WPs will build an international open working group that will analyse the current and future Copernicus services from their specific perspective. The working groups will coordinate their activities as much as possible to support cross-topic discussions. Each of the technical WPs will produce their recommendations for the Roadmap.

The second overarching WP (**WP6**) will summarise the findings of each technical WP and produce the first draft of the Roadmap. After reviewing and discussing it with stakeholders the WP6 will provide a consensus Roadmap, as the final outcome of the Water-ForCE project, to relevant bodies like the European Commission, ESA, EEA, JRC, national space agencies, national monitoring and regulatory agencies, research communities and industry.

3 Overall Strategy

The establishment of a concise communication strategy with a predetermined scope and carefully defined goals is essential in order to develop communication activities in an efficient way. This strategy has been designed and will be followed as closely as possible during the project course. The Water-ForCE Communication strategy will be based on Laswell model of five levels of communication (shown in table 1 below), (who - Source, what - Message, in which channel or through which medium, to whom – the audience, and to what effect) and is developed in accordance with the European Commission’s recommendations on Communication/ Dissemination.

Question	Element	Analysis (outcome)
Who?	Communicat or	Control Analysis
Says What?	Message	Content Analysis
In which channel? How?	Medium	Media Analysis
	Audience	Audience Analysis
To Whom?	Effect	Effects Analysis

Table 1: Water-ForCE communication strategy based on Laswell model

The communication strategy includes the definition of communication goals, target groups, communication channels and materials. This means that for each project phase there is a clear plan of cost-efficient communication means, so as to reach the specified target groups through the defined communication channels with the scope of achieving the communication goals.

In short, the communication and dissemination activities of WaterForCE aim to:

- To contact stakeholders, researchers and users in the inland water domain
- To adjust dissemination activities to every type of user
- To use innovative tools and activities to effectively engage dialogue with stakeholders

4 Who: Dissemination and Outreach target groups

Water-ForCE has a dedicated task in WP1 to identify key user communities and groups within the different public domains and business sectors and each WP will create a working group including all relevant actors. As already explained, the project's purpose to create a user and stakeholder driven concept for water services, needs to reach all kinds of users and stakeholders. It can be seen as a 2D matrix that needs to be filled. The different dimensions of that matrix would be the distinct type of target group according to:

- nature of the institution they belong and
- the water related variable they are interested in

On top of this, stakeholders should also cover the following aspects:

- the different types of water surface identified and
- different geographical level of activities

In order to manage this dissemination and outreach, we have adopted the HubSpot Customer Relationship Management Software (CRM) (<https://www.hubspot.com/>) tool.

The initial groups of users identified by the nature of the institution they belong are the following:

- Group 1: Regulators and Policy Makers
- Group 2: Commercial Users of Water Data
- Group 3: In-sector Business and Industry
- Group 4: Researchers, Agencies, NGOs

The water related variables of interest are clustered as in the technical WPs:

- Water quality continuum (WP2),
- Water quantity (WP3),
- In situ and satellite Earth observation activities (WP4) and
- Modelling and data assimilation (WP5).

The different aquatic systems currently identified are the following:

- Lakes
- Reservoirs
- Rivers

- Estuaries
- Coastal
- Wetlands
- Groundwater
- Lagoons
- Ocean / marine

The different Geographical level of activities

- Catchment
- International / intergovernmental
- Local
- National
- Regional

5 What: Content

WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 will generate different content, information and results that will be of value to the different target groups. The different Working Groups will analyse the current and future Copernicus services from their specific perspective.

Some of the key information to be gathered is:

- What water-related information are users interested in
- What are the biggest barriers to the uptake of satellite remote sensing in the water domain? and
- What are the biggest information needs with regards to satellite remote sensing?

6 How: Dissemination Strategy

6.1 Overall Strategy

Effective and efficient dissemination requires making use of a variety of appropriate tools. The Water-ForCE outreach and dissemination plan defines specific dissemination tools for each of the target groups as indicated in the following Table:

Target Groups	Planned Actions
In-sector Business and Industry, Commercial Users of Water Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to specialised exhibitions and conferences • Direct contact to possibly interested companies • Link to other European projects
Regulators and Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Open Workshops • Participation to specialised exhibitions and conferences • Direct contact to possibly interested associations
Researchers, Agencies, NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to other European projects • Organisation of workshops • Link with other R&D centres and scientific organizations • Participation to national and international conferences • Articles, reports in scientific and technical journals
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project reference identity • Public area of the project web site • Other dissemination materials (webinars, multimedia releases, e-newsletters)
Project Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project management board, workshops, and technical meetings • e-Newsletter • Initiatives for students of the universities participating to the project • Seminars & tutorials • Internal mailing lists

Table 2: Adopted tools according to target group.

6.2 Project reference identity

A common reference identity in all dissemination tasks allows for better visibility and recognition as well as branding of the project. Furthermore, all publications and presentations by members of the project consortium must acknowledge the H2020 financial support received.

All dissemination tools and activities refer to the name of the project, to the project's website URL (<https://waterforce.eu/>) and to the graphic elements described in this section.

6.2.1 Project logo

Figure 1: Water-ForCE project logo

The project's logo shown above is an abstract representation of a river and a lake and has been developed to be used with different colors and sizes. It has been approved by the consortium partners as the official logo for the project and will be used for any (internal or external) deliverable, report and dissemination tool.

6.2.2 H2020 logo

Figure 2: H2020 logo

The Water-ForCE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004186.

The H2020 logo is used for any (internal or external) deliverable, report and dissemination tool.

How to display the acknowledgment of EU funding:

Type of communication	Placement of logo / guidelines for use
Website & Social media account	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same place on every page • Ideally as part of the website frame which appears on all sections • Landing or intro page (social media)
Brochure, information leaflet, factsheet, newsletter, poster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bottom right corner of publication • Front or back cover • On white background (unless placed on a large photo or illustration as on a poster)

Type of communication	Placement of logo / guidelines for use
Report & internal project publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Front cover
Power Point or other graphical presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First or last slide of a presentation or in the footer of each slide
Video & animation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intro or closing screenshot

Table 3: How to display the acknowledgment of EU funding.

6.2.3 Layouts

Common layouts are used for the Water-ForCE dissemination materials. These include templates for deliverables, leaflets, posters and website and PowerPoint presentations.

6.2.4 Publications

All publications issued from Water-ForCE partnership will be published either in gold or green access (leave it to the institution discretion) and funding from the project acknowledged in the following way:

“The Water-ForCE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004186”.

6.3 Dissemination Channels

6.3.1 Project Web Page

A dedicated web site has been developed. The project web site is allocated at:

<https://waterforce.eu/>

The main aim of the website will be to provide a general resource to support the building of a community. It will also provide a unified view of the project, publicising and highlighting the activities of Water-ForCE.

The website will be maintained and kept up to date by isardSAT, as the lead on WP7.

Consideration will be given to the use of social media (e.g. Twitter) to promote the website and the project. Optimisation techniques will be used to ensure the visibility of the Water-ForCE website.

The domain has been registered (WaterForCE.eu) and hosting will continue for at least 2 years beyond the project's end date to ensure the legacy of the project.

This external-facing part of the website will include among other items:

- An overall description of the project and its objectives, information sheets and other publicity material for the project which will be available for download.
- Details of the project consortium with links to their sites, likewise consortium members will set up links to the Water-ForCE website on their own websites.
- News from the project and consortium members.
- Publicity and information about events put on as part of the project such as Workshops as well as Conferences where the Water-ForCE project and its results are presented.
- Scientific papers and presentations by the members of the consortium and other papers of interest.
- A method for contacting the project, a way of joining the project mailing list and information on how to contribute to the project and in particular to the roadmap.
- The publicly available deliverables for the project as they are completed.

6.3.2 Social Media

The project's Social Media are a key tool for external one-way communication. A twitter account (@h2020WaterForCE) and a LinkedIn commercial page (linkedin.com/company/Water-ForCE) have been created and will be regularly fed to keep the audience informed, bringing them to the website and ensuring interest of already attracted visitors.

Social media channels will be fed by news and updated content on the website and other contents published by the stakeholders involved in the sector and related to the Water-ForCE project. It will allow to create an active and participatory community of followers around the project, and to increase the visits on the website. They also allow establishing links with other consistent R&I initiatives by following dedicated accounts.

- LinkedIn will be used to promote project actions among policy makers and stakeholders and foster networking.
- Twitter will be used to promote project actions and messages among stakeholders, mass media and general public and foster networking.

6.4 Dissemination activities

6.4.1 Workshops and Seminars

In order to reach new stakeholders and engage current stakeholders, it is planned that each technical WP organises at least one thematic WS. These workshops are open with the idea to engage collaboration and receive feedback from the scientific community and stakeholders.

An indicative date and place of the Water-ForCE workshops is provided in Table 4.

WP	Name	Date	Place
WP3	On the use of remote sensing for monitoring and modelling the water cycle	March 15, 2021	Online
WP1	Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services	April 20th, 2021	Online
WP2- WP4	In situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology	May 17th, 18th and 20th, 2021	Online
WP7	International Stakeholder Workshop		
	- online event during Water Innovation Europe 2021	June 14-18, 2021	Online
	- presential event	October 2021	Copenhagen
WP7	Water-ForCE final Workshop	March 2023	Brussels

Table 4: Scheduled Water-ForCE workshops.

Clearly, other workshop and seminar opportunities outside the Water-ForCE project will also be explored.

6.4.2 e-Newsletters

Electronic newsletters will be prepared quarterly, providing information on results achieved in the project and upcoming activities. The e-newsletters will be distributed by email through hubspot. The mailing list will be used according to the GDPR guidelines and managed for this purpose.

The first newsletter is expected to be released in August 2021 (M8).

6.4.3 Scientific Papers and Conferences

The scientific community will be informed about Water-ForCE and its main achievements through publications in peer reviewed international journals and conferences. The targeted journals are: Water Resources Research, Water Resources Management, Journal of Hydrometeorology, Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology, Agricultural and Water Management, Remote Sensing of Environment, Remote Sensing.

They will also be presented in **symposia** such as the European Geoscience Union (EGU), the American Geoscience Union (AGU), International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS), Recent Advances in Quantitative Remote Sensing (RAQRS), Specialist Meeting on Microwave Radiometry and Remote Sensing of the Environment (MICRORAD) and ESA Earth Observation for Water Cycle Science conference and Living Planet Symposium.

6.5 Communication activities

Finally, the communication will also include activities aiming at the general EU community about the results of the project and how these results could be relevant to the general public such as:

Multimedia Releases: a mini video to be published on our website and some public channels.

e-Newsletters: to be released by project partners in their respective networks;

Articles in Newspapers: Submit an article / press release to be published in Science and Technology supplements of newspapers in the host country.

7 Expected impact of the proposed measures

The expected impact of the proposed dissemination and outreach activities is the effective consolidation of a network and the effective reaching of the WATER community.

Success in the communication, dissemination and outreach activities will be measured by the key performance indicators (KPI) presented below:

Indicator	KPI (end of second period)	KPI (end of CSA)
Number of unique website visitors	3000	4000
Stakeholders registered in Hubspot	200	600
Participation in Workshops and Conferences	10	20
Number of special sessions hosted in conferences	3	6
Journal Papers	2	5
Followers on Twitter	200	300
Twitter activity: number of tweets	40	80
Followers on LinkedIn	100	200
Posts on LinkedIn profile	15	30
Followers on vimeo	50	100
Videos produced	24	50
Newsletters published	2	5
Number of organised Workshops	6	8
Participants to Water-Force Workshops	250	500
Number of organised webinars	7	15
Attendants to webinars	120	300

Table 5: KPI for Outreach and Communications activities

8 Conclusions

This document has presented a comprehensive dissemination strategy specifying a common project reference identity, specific tools and activities adapted to the respective target groups, as well as an internal assessment procedure.

The dissemination plan described in the document therefore presents the overall process that will be followed by the consortium to optimize the awareness of the project's output as well as the dissemination of project results to all relevant stakeholders, both at a general level as well as at the level of each individual research outcome.

To further improve the dissemination strategy, the dissemination plan will be updated during the project's lifetime as the project advances and the feedback from stakeholders accumulates.